

Assessment of Rural Development Project in Gidan Waya, Jema'a L.G.A, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract:- The main purpose of the research is to assess rural development project in GidanWaya. The research seeks to identify the rural development strategy put in place in GidanWaya, identify the categories of rural development project in GidanWaya, assess who are they provider of rural development project in GidanWaya, assess where the rural development projects are located in GidanWaya and examine the impact of the rural development project on the social life of GidanWaya people. The study uses hundred numbers (100) questionnaires that were shared to respondents in the study area to obtained information regarding rural development project in GidanWaya. The data were analyzed through the use of descriptive statistical techniques and presented using percentage, tables, and figures. Finding reveals that GidanWaya community is having Motor Park and that going in and outside GidanWaya is easy as taxi are accessible at any time of the day, in the aspect of light, the area do have an epileptic power supply in the area which serve as a deterrent for underdevelopment of the area and the inhabitant are not satisfied with the happenings. The study concludes that rural development is the activities and actions of diverse actors, individual, organisations, and groups which when taken together leads to progress in rural areas. The study therefore recommends that Public rural development initiatives whether politically or socially motivated should be subjected to proper, social cost-benefit analysis before implementation. These projects should continually be monitored and reviewed when necessary especially when inflation has set in.

Keywords:- Rural area, rural development project, and Gidan Waya.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the greatest problems of third world countries today is the high rate of rural urban drift, making the population in the cities, more difficult to manage. This rural urban drift poses serious challenges to the third world countries as only very few city governments have the resources and facilities to cope with such rapidly growing population (Otto, 2018).

The major cause of the high exodus to the urban areas is the neglect of rural areas, in spite of the fact that over 65 percent of Nigerians are rural dwellers. The rural areas are generally characterized by high level of illiteracy, abject poverty, unemployment and lack of other basic infrastructural facilities including housing, electricity and inadequate communication facilities, though in 2002

President Obasanjo introduced the GSM services which have been extended to semi-urban areas (Otto, 2018). The standard of living is generally low, this has partly informed the drift to urban areas where basic facilities are relatively more available and standards of living are higher.

The rural areas in general would require a new deal in the provision of social services. In almost every state, sizeable communities still exist without basic amenities, like clean water supply, hospitals and health centres, schools and electricity (Ihonvere, 2017).

Rural development is the activities and actions of diverse actors, individual, organizations and groups which when taken together leads to progress in rural areas. Rural development strategy is a mechanism designed to improve the economic and social life of those who live in rural areas. Embarking on rural development is very important considering the fact that more than two-third of the Nigeria's population are living in rural areas, and they experience a lot of misery, poverty, morbidity and underdevelopment. Reflection on the Nigerian Government experiences in rural development showed that not much has been achieved even before and after independence. There exists a sharp contrast between policy formulation and its implementation. The resultant effect becomes more hardship and poor standard of living among the rural dwellers. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop a functional rural development strategy that will be used to salvage the crumbling productive nature of the study area (Diejemaoh, 2013).

Quite a number of these projects have failed, and government dreams in changing the living conditions of rural areas are far from being realised. This work reviews some of these rural projects and programmes with a view to isolate sources and militating factors inhibiting the realization of government dreams in GidanWaya. To do this, a sample of such projects was used, which served as basis for the analysis. This work therefore attempts to identify problems affecting rural development initiatives by the government in Gidan Waya from 2010 to 2009.

II. STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Due to the erroneous belief held by politicians and some government officials, without any professional outlook, that the urban areas constitute the developmental potential for any state, the rural area has been neglected and attention has being focused on the urban area. This belief has led to the neglect, underdevelopment, underutilization, of resources in the rural area. Living conditions in the rural

area is nothing to write home about, an assessment of the present situation of our rural area, exhibit the exact indication of abject poverty. Urban problems such as housing, inadequate transportation system, basic recreational facilities, and consequential effect of unemployment like increase in crime rate, kidnapping, and environmental problems because of huge concentration of industries in these urban centres have on a consistent basis consumed a large portion of the state annual budget expenditures.

GidanWaya is a community in Jema'a Local Government of Area of Kaduna State which is undergoing a serious problem of underdevelopment despite its population constitutes students from different walks of life as a result of Kaduna College of Education instituted in the area. The college provided by the government in the area has not been given proper attention in term of development despite revenue generated by the school to the government since it development in the year 1977 the school has suffered insufficient classes for lectures, hostel for students abundant as no students occupying because its bad, road from school gate to the school is interred making the road difficult to walk on during wet season. road linking other environs to GidanWaya community are in need of attention as no maintenance of the road by the government as other body as required, provision of social amenities is nothing to write home about in the area.

This study focused on assessment of rural development project in GidanWaya looking at the neglect, underdevelopment, and underutilization of resources in the area and living conditions in the area is nothing to write home about.

The specific goals of this research are to: identify the categories of rural development project in GidanWaya, assess who are they provider of rural development project in GidanWaya, assess where the rural development projects are located in GidanWaya, and examine the impact of the rural development project on the social life of GidanWaya people.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

GidanWaya is in Jema'a Local Government area of Kaduna State, in Northern Nigeria, which lies between latitudes 9°27'30" and 9°25'29" North of the equator and longitudes 8°25'45" and 9°27'30" East of the Greenwich meridian showing the square coordinate of the area. The elevation of GidanWaya is 556metre above sea level. The coordinate of the community was collected using a conventional survey method, which GPS instrument was used in capturing the data in the field by the researcher.

GidanWaya in Jema'a Local Government Area experiences an annual rainfall of 150mm (Ishaya and Abaje, 2008). The area has a unimodal rainfall distribution in which

rain increases in frequency and amount, beginning in May and peaking in August, this makes the area arable and support the cultivation of various food and cash crops,

including rearing of animals. The temperature of the area is high with mean monthly temperature of 28°C while the relative humidity is about 52.66% (Ishaya and Abaje, 2008).

According to National population census (2006) based on Jema'a Local Government Area, GidanWaya comprises of linear scattered settlements with a population of about 35,200 people. The dwellers of GidanWaya largely depend on agricultural practices, and also other forms of farming. Gwandara, Numana and Kagoro people are the dominant ethnic groups in the area, followed by Fantswam, Bajju, Hausa, Kaninkon and other migrants. GidanWaya community is served, by a single centrally located Government secondary and primary school built and operates primarily by the local government; private school operates by individual, a private clinic that provides basic preventive and curative services to the people of the community (Chief of GidanWaya, 2021).

Economically, GidanWaya is a community that the majority are agro farmers, and few civil servants. They engaged into irrigation farming of perishable farm produce during the dry season and also cultivate crops like: yam, cassava, maize, beans, millet, sorghum, rice, ginger, and groundnut, and some other crops during rainy season. A significant number of families are involved in livestock production. The important livestock reared include poultry, cattle, sheep, goats and pigs. Small scale farmers dominate the agricultural production in the area (Joyce, 2011).

IV. PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION

A cross sectional research design was adopted for the study. It involved the selection of a sample to represent the target population in the study area. A hundred (100) respondents were selected through the simple random sampling technique out of the 35,200 (NPC, 2006) population that makes up GidanWaya.

A wide range of collected primary data required for the study included the demographic characteristics of respondents; categories of rural development project in GidanWaya, the provider of rural development project in GidanWaya, the rural development projects location in GidanWaya, and the impact of the rural development project on the social life of GidanWaya people. The responses sought for were through a series of questions with a number of options for the respondents to tick appropriately the ones that appeal to them, but may freely make comments. The sources of the other information for the study were: the National Population Commission (NPC, 2006) for the population of the study area; Kaduna Geographic Information Service for the published map of GidanWaya;

while relevant literature were obtained from textbooks, articles in academic journals and through internet searches.

A semi-structured questionnaire, which served as the main instrument, was constructed for the data collection exercise from the field.

In order to test the validity of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted in the study area. This was done to detect ambiguous questions and difficult expressions and amend them before the real field exercise.

In determining the sample size of the study area, Yaro Yamani's (1964) formula was used. The formula is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where; n = Sample size

N = Population

1 = Constant

(e) 2 = Margin Error

Note: this study allowed ten (10) percent margin of error in calculating the optimal sample size (i.e. 0.1). Noting that the population size (N) in this case is 35,200 the estimated sample size was calculated as:

$$n = \frac{35200}{1 + 35200(0.1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{35200}{35201(0.01)}$$

$$n = \frac{35200}{352}$$

$$n = 100$$

Approximate sample size then became:

$$n=100$$

The total number of questionnaires administered was 100 for the purpose of this study. A hundred copies of the questionnaire were distributed to selected respondents from the study area using the simple random sampling technique; ninety-eight copies of the questionnaires were dully filled and returned for analysis.

The descriptive statistical technique in the form of frequency counts, percentages and charts were used to analyse the data obtained from the field based on the above stated objectives of the study. Literature reviews were obtained from secondary sources, particularly textbooks, articles in learned journals, and internet searches.

V. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

• Demographic characteristics of respondents

The profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex of Respondents		
Male	61	62
Female	37	38
Total	98	100
Age of respondents		
15-25 years	26	27
26-40 years	49	50
41-60 years	16	16
61 years and above	7	7
Total	98	100
Educational Background of Respondents		
None	5	5
Primary	29	30
Secondary	48	49
Tertiary	16	16
Total	98	100
Marital Status of Respondents		
Single	32	33
Married	56	57
Divorced	2	2
Widow	8	8
Total	98	100
Occupational Status of Respondents		
Trader	20	21
Farmer	42	43
Driver	5	5
Teacher	7	7
Unemployment	1	1
Business	13	13
Civil servant	10	10
Total	98	100

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of respondents

Source: Author's Analysis, 2022

• Categories of Rural Development Project in GidanWaya

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Road construction	26	27
Electricity provision	18	18
Provision of water	6	6
Building of schools	38	39
Agricultural enhancement or subsidies	8	8
Job creation	2	2
Education subsidies	0	0
Total	98	100

Table 2: Rural Development Project in GidanWaya

Source: Author's Analysis, 2022

Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents said the rural development project in their area is school building having 39%, 27% road construction, 18% electricity provision, 8% agricultural enhancement/subsidies, 6% provision of water while 2% of the respondents said job creation is the rural development project provided in the area. The result implies that building of school is the major

rural development provided in the area and these are Kaduna College of Education, government as well as private schools within.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Road	31	32
Electricity provision	16	16
Provision of water	5	5
Schools	46	47
Total	98	100

Table 3: Pronounce Rural Development Project in the Area

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 3 shows that school is the most pronounce rural development project in the area that is obvious having 47%, road having 32%, electricity provision having 16% while provision of water is the least obvious project in the area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Road	9	9
Electricity provision	16	16
Provision of water	41	42
Schools	32	33
Total	98	100

Table 4: Rural Development Project Most Neglected in the Area

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 4 shows that provision of water is a project that is neglected in the area and not properly maintain by it provider having 42%, 33% schools, 16% electricity provision while 9% for road construction. Based on ranking from the result provided by respondents, water is life but it’s neglected and that brings untold hardly to people living in the area.

Fig. 1: Prevalent Means of Transportation Within and Outside the Community

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Figure 1 shows that 67% of the respondents admitted that the prevalent means of transportation within and outside the community is taxi, 28% okada while 5% of the respondents admitted that bicycle is the prevalent means of

transportation within and outside GidanWaya community. The state of the major road linking the community of GidanWaya is in bad state and need immediate attention.

• Provider of Rural Development Project in GidanWaya

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Government	54	55
NGO	3	3
Private individuals	5	5
Government and NGO	9	9
Government and private individuals	27	28
NGO and private individuals	0	0
Total	98	100

Table 5: Provider of Rural Development Project in Your Community

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 5 shows that 55% of the respondents admitted that the government are the provider of rural development in their community, 28% of the respondents admitted that both government and private individuals, 9% of the respondents

admitted that both government and NGOs, 5% of the respondents admitted that private individuals while 3% of the respondents admitted that the NGOs are the provider of rural development project in their community.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Schools	57	58
Hospital	9	10
Roads	13	13
Power supply	19	19
Market	0	0
Others	0	0
Total	98	100

Table 6: Rural Development Project Provided by the Government/NGOs

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 6 shows that majority of the respondents in the area admitted that schools are the rural development project in the area provided by Government/NGOS having 58%,

19% power supply, 13% roads construction, while 10% is hospital that is provided by the Government/NGOs in the area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Roads	0	0
Hospital	21	21
Schools	31	32
Power supply	0	0
Market	46	47
Others	0	0
Total	98	100

Table 7: Rural Development Project Provided by the Community/Private Individuals

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 7 shows that 47% of rural development project provided by the community/private individuals is market, 32% schools, while 21% hospitals that were provided by the

community/private individual as rural development project in the area. Most of the projects provided are by private individual with exception of the market.

• Rural Development Projects Locations in GidanWaya

S/n	Location	Rural Development Project
1	Mile one	Government Primary
2	UngwarShuwaka	College of education GidanWaya
3	UngwarKaje	Transformer, PHC, Private schools
4	Jos Road	Market, Private Filling Station

Table 8: Rural Development Project Located in GidanWaya

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 8 shows the various locations where the provided rural development projected in GidanWaya are situated which are; Mile one, UngwarShuwaka, ungwarKaje, and Jos Road area of GidanWaya.

• Impact of the Rural Development Project on the Social Life of GidanWaya People

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	10	10
No	88	90
Total	98	100

Table 9: Adequate Rural Development Project forGidanWaya Community bythe Government

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 9 shows that there is no adequate rural development project by the government in the area having 90% while 10% of the respondents said there is. The result implies that there is provision of rural development project in the area but it's not adequate.

Fig. 2: Rating of Rural Development Project in GidanWaya Community

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Figure 2 show that 71% of the respondents say the rural development project in GidanWaya community is not satisfactory while 29% of the respondents say the rural development project in GidanWaya community is

satisfactory. Based on the rating of the rural development project been poor, it is clearly seen that there are no proper maintenance of provided development project in the area.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	20	20
No	78	80
Total	98	100

Table 10: If Infrastructures Provided for the Community Meets the Demand of the Inhabitant?

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 10 shows that 80% of the respondents says that the infrastructures provided for the community do not meets the demand of the inhabitant while 20% of the respondents

admitted that the infrastructure provided for the community meets the demand of the inhabitant.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of finance	25	26
Lack of concern from government	68	69
Youths and politicians	5	5
Total	98	100

Table 11: Problem of Rural Development Project in GidanWaya

Source: Author’s Analysis, 2022

Table 11 shows that 69% of the respondents said that lack of concern from government is the problem of rural development project in GidanWaya, 26% of the respondents said lack of finance to sponsor project is the problem of rural development project in the area while 5% of the respondents said that youths and politicians are the problem of rural development project in GidanWaya.

table 2, followed by road and others. Kaduna State College of Education is one of the schools provided by government for the development of the area, a government secondary school and primary school.

Study discovered that water supply is neglected in the area as such they undergo untold hardship to acquire water from streams, river and hand dug well. The provided boreholes got bad but due to no maintenance neither repairs of the boreholes in the area.

VI. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Finding shows that the obvious project provided to GidanWaya community is schools having 39% as shown in

Finding shows that the government, NGOs, community and private individual were responsible for the provision of existing development project in the area but large provision was done by individuals.

Table 8 shows the various locations where the provided rural development projected in GidanWaya are situated which are; Mile one, UngwarShuwaka, UngwarKaje, and Jos Road area of GidanWaya.

Finding shows that there is no adequate rural development project by the government in the area, while the ones provided are not up to satisfactory level by people in the community as most of the project were abandon with no maintenance.

Finding shows that lack of concern from the government is the problem of rural development project in GidanWaya, e.g Kaduna State College of Education since inception the road from the school gate to inside the school have not been paved, no enough classes for lectures while there is increasing population of student's year in year out.

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, Rural development is the activities and actions of diverse actors, individual, organisations, and groups which when taken together leads to progress in rural areas. The dynamism of the rural sector is imbedded in it capacity to act as a major support to it corresponding urban areas, therefore it's development should be treated with utmost concern and technicality. The strategies of rural development are numerous, the end product of the used strategy in any development should be of paramount concern as the life of people are jeopardize if not suitable to the host community.

From the findings of this research and the conclusions drawn therefrom, the following recommendations are made:

- There should be high consideration for the participation of the concerned community or people in order to arrive at an efficient and sustainable mode of rural development.
- Public rural development initiatives whether politically or socially motivated should be subjected to proper, social cost-benefit analysis before implementation. These projects should continually be monitored and reviewed when necessary especially when inflation has set in.
- To ensure continuity, it may be important to suggest that governments should concert efforts to complete abandoned projects. New projects should be fully discussed before commencement and once started; the initiators must take responsibility for the completion of the projects.
- Government should provide the enabling environment to foster rural and community development in Nigeria. Facilities such as education, health services, electricity supply, improving literacy, health and general quality of life are acutely inadequate in the rural areas.

- Rural development in Nigeria should not be the concern of only Federal, State and local governments. It is important that individuals, communities, corporate organizations, non-governmental organizations and international organizations and agencies should be deeply involved in the efforts at eradicating poverty, enhancing rural development and the overall national development of the country.

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